

SHORE

Empower students as the agents of change

D5.2 – Plan for Communication, Dissemination, and Outreach v2

Date of delivery – 31/12/2024

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Full name
CH	Country Hubs
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
NEBS	Network of European Blue Schools
PCDO	Plan for communication, dissemination, and outreach
WP	Work Package

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Background about the SHORE Project

SHORE strives to increase ocean literacy by engaging students and teachers to implement the EU Mission Ocean & Water' objectives through activities and collaborative projects in schools.

Within this project, the project partners will craft trainings and educational materials in line with blue curricula for schools located in the Baltic Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Danube River, and Rhine River. Participating schools will secure grants to support the implementation of their blue projects. The most outstanding school projects will be awarded "Ocean Ambassador of the Year". Beyond awarding grants, SHORE serves as a comprehensive resource hub and a bridge between researchers, local stakeholders, and schools in the regional areas.

Executive summary

This document is a deliverable of the Mission Ocean & Waters SHORE Project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101112815. SHORE is part of the EU Mission "Restore our Oceans & Waters by 2030".

This deliverable is the updated version of the Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Outreach (PCDO) as part of Work Package 5 on Communication, Dissemination, and Outreach. It provides the SHORE partners with guidelines on the different communication, dissemination and outreach activities that are planned throughout the project, their schedule, and the partners' responsibilities

More specifically, the PCDO:

- proposes a communication and dissemination policy and defines the objectives of the actions;
- identifies the target audiences of the project;
- lists the communication and dissemination channels to be used for project promotion;
- presents a schedule of the communication, dissemination, and outreach activities throughout the project duration;
- identifies relevant stakeholders and presents the project's strategy for engagement, clustering, and networking;
- presents the awareness-raising campaigns that will be implemented by the project;
- defines and monitors a series of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess the success of the implementation.

The document is drafted by Euronovia (WP5 leader) and Crowdhelix (leader of the stakeholders engagement and clustering activities), with inputs from all partners.

A final report on the project communication, dissemination, and outreach activities (D5.5) is planned by M34.

1. Introduction

1.1. Definitions and terminology

SHORE distinguishes between communication and dissemination, in line with the EC definitions below, as well as outreach.

Communication is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the project and continues throughout its entire lifetime. It is aimed at promoting SHORE and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about SHORE and results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. Activities used for communication purposes are, for example, a public website, social media, or a newsletter.

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the project results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protection or exploitation of results), including scientific publication in any medium. It is the process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups (e.g., research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers) in a targeted way, enabling them to use the results in their own work. This process must be planned and organised at the beginning of each project. Tools and activities used for dissemination purposes are, for example, a public website, press releases, publications, and attendance of events.

Outreach is a continuous and strategic engagement process that extends beyond the project's immediate boundaries involving efforts to connect with a diverse audience throughout the entire project duration. Outreach is the process of explaining and sharing knowledge and involves purposeful efforts to raise awareness and connect with a wider audience through various activities, such as popularisation events, webinars, and strategic partnerships with similar projects. Outreach seeks to build sustained connections, ensuring that the project remains dynamically linked with a wide range of stakeholders after the duration of the project.

1.2. General rules and procedures

1.1.1. Communication within the SHORE Consortium

Communication among partners is crucial to exchange up-to-date knowledge and data on activities implemented within the different WPs and to enhance and optimise external communication and dissemination.

Internal communication is ensured through regular exchange of information via e-mail, through the SHORE management platform and during regular meetings, when all partners gather to discuss achievements, upcoming activities, deadlines, and issues arising within the different work packages.

Communication and dissemination activities are coordinated by Euronovia, with the support of Crowdhelix and YTU. **All partners regularly participate in communication and dissemination activities**, namely by:

- communicating their activities and disseminating their results to their respective networks, for instance via their own social media accounts and websites;
- contributing to the content of the SHORE social media accounts, website, and bi-annual newsletter;
- informing the other partners of relevant initiatives, activities, and events they could participate in;
- keeping track of their communication and dissemination activities by filling in a dedicated reporting table available in the project's document repository (see Annex 1);
- disseminating results in open access publications, conferences, and other relevant events.

1.1.2. Use of graphic identity and EU and Mission Ocean and Waters visibility

A common graphic identity has been defined to allow for better visibility and recognition, as well as branding of the SHORE project. Therefore, all dissemination tools and activities must refer to or include:

- The SHORE project logo (different versions are available depending on the background colour and document format)
- The name of the project: SHORE
- Information on EU funding (as defined in Article 17 of the GA):
 - Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must: (a) display the EU emblem and (b) include the following text: "Funded by the European Union".
 - Any communication and dissemination activity must also indicate the following disclaimer: "Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."
 - When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must be given appropriate prominence.
 - Specific guidelines regarding the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes 2021-2027 can be found on the [EC website](#).
- Whenever possible, information on the Mission Ocean & Waters:
 - Visual identity of the Mission Ocean (graphical elements and name)
 - The sentence "SHORE is part of the EU Mission Ocean & Waters"

Rules for the schools receiving SHORE funding

Schools receiving funding from the SHORE project must highlight the financial support of the EC and SHORE. The rules are detailed in Article 9 of the sub-grant agreement (D6.2) that they will sign and are copied below (in case of discrepancy between Article 9 and the present document, the sub-agreement should always be the reference). In the text below “Beneficiary” refers to the schools receiving SHORE funding.

Unless the EC requests otherwise, any publicity, including at a conference or seminar or any type of information or promotional material (brochure, leaflet, poster, presentation, etc.), and any infrastructure, equipment, and major results must:

- Specify that the sub-project has received research funding from the EC through the SHORE project.
- Display the European emblem along with the SHORE logo. When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem should be given appropriate prominence. This obligation to use the European emblem in respect of projects to which the EC contributes implies no right of exclusive use. It is subject to general third-party use restrictions which do not permit the appropriation of the emblem, or of any similar trademark or logo, whether by registration or by any other means. Under these conditions, the Beneficiary is exempt from the obligation to obtain prior permission from the EC to use the emblem.
- Specify that it reflects only the author’s views and that the EC and the SHORE Consortium is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The following text should be used: “The [sub-project acronym] has indirectly received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation action programme, via the SHORE – Open Call #2 issued and executed under the SHORE project (Grant Agreement no. 101112815).”
- Whenever possible, information on the Mission Ocean & Waters:
 - Visual identity of the Mission Ocean (graphical elements and name)
 - The sentence “SHORE is part of the EU Mission Ocean & Waters”
- Specific guidelines regarding the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes 2021-2027 can be found on the [EC website](#).

1.1.3. Open access to scientific publications

Open access is defined by the EC as the online access to research outputs provided free of charge to the end-user (Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement). It is mandatory under Horizon Europe, and it operates on the principle of being ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’. The SHORE partners are committed to publishing scientific publications in open access. SHORE will follow the Open Science Policy of the Horizon Europe Programme and apply Open Science Practices to all methodologies, research results, deliverables, policy and scientific publications, as well as to data that is not subject to GDPR. As required by the EC, all publications will be made immediately accessible.

The platform Sherpa/Romeo (<http://www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/index.php>) will be used to have a summary of permissions that are normally given as part of each publisher's copyright transfer agreement.

Further to this and whenever necessary, the addendum to the publication agreement provided by the EC will be used. This is an instrument that, if accepted by the editor, modifies the publisher's agreement, and allows the researcher to keep key rights to your articles. The coordinator will support the researchers for these administrative issues related to the communication with the publishers.

All publications and accompanying data are stored in the online project community created by Euronovia on Zenodo ([available at this link](#)). All uploads are thus be directly indexed in OpenAIRE. The SHORE Zenodo Community is part of the [EU Open Research Repository](#).

1.1.4. Open access to scientific data

The project will collect relevant research data that will be managed according to the Data Management Plan prepared by the coordinator YTU (D1.2) respecting the principle that open scientific research data should be easily discoverable, accessible, useable, and wherever possible interoperable to specific quality standards. The SHORE partners will carefully study the possibility and pertinence of making each dataset findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

Data will be shared in accordance with recognised standards used in the research field, to maximise the opportunities for data linkage and interoperability. Sufficient metadata will be provided to enable the datasets to be used by others. Generally, the data being produced will be shared and made accessible for verification and re-use, according to the provisions foreseen in the Consortium Agreement. Access to specific data may be restricted under limited circumstances (e.g., to protect personal data, to protect the beneficiary's legitimate interests, etc.).

1.1.5. Ethics

Consent form for pictures

The SHORE project actively involves children through their participation in the funded schools' "Blue Projects." To ensure proper communication and dissemination of the project's outcomes, schools and parents must be fully informed about the use of any pictures or videos captured during these activities.

A standard consent form was meticulously drafted by YTU as part of Work Package 7 (WP7) on Ethics. This document, in line with the European Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR) requirements, outlines the terms and conditions for using such materials. The consent form is distributed to participating schools through the project partners, ensuring that parental agreements for the use of photos and videos are secured in advance. This process reflects the project's commitment to ethical standards and transparency.

Publication of schools' information

For the purposes of the project's communication and dissemination activities, the partners will publish information related to the schools. This sharing will be done in collaboration with the schools. Nevertheless, by receiving SHORE funding, the schools agree to the sharing of some of their information. The rules are detailed in Article 9 of the sub-grant agreement that they will sign and are copied below (in case of discrepancy between Article 9 and the present document, the sub-agreement should always be the reference). In the text below, "Beneficiary" refers to the schools receiving SHORE funding.

The Coordinator, the SHORE consortium, and/or the EC shall be authorised to publish, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, the following information:

- The name of the Beneficiary.
- Contact address of the Beneficiary.
- The general purpose of the sub-project (publishable summary, etc.)
- The amount of the financial contribution of the EC foreseen for the sub-project. after the final payment, the amount and rate of the financial contribution of the EC accepted by the EC.
- The estimated amount and rate of the financial contribution of the EC foreseen for the Beneficiary are in the table of the estimated breakdown of the budget.
- The geographic location of the activities carried out.
- The list of dissemination activities and/or of patent (applications) relating to foreground.
- The publishable reports submitted (technical reports are excluded, since they are confidential).
- Any picture or any audio-visual or web material provided to the EC in the framework of the Sub-project.

The Beneficiary shall ensure that all necessary authorisations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the SHORE Coordinator, the SHORE consortium partners, or EC does not infringe any rights of third parties.

2. Communication, Dissemination, and Outreach Strategy

2.1. Phases

The planning and execution of the project communication, dissemination, and outreach activities require a schedule closely aligned with key project deliverables, milestones, activities, and the three open calls. In this framework, our activities are organised around one initial phase (M1-M6), the phases related to the three open calls (M6-M33), and the final phase dedicated to the presentation of the results (M33-M36).

During the initial phase (M1-M6), the emphasis was on developing a comprehensive communication strategy that outlines key messages, target audiences, and the selection of appropriate communication channels. In this phase, we developed the project website and various communication and dissemination materials, including the project graphical identity (i.e., project logo, branding guidelines, templates for project documents and presentations). In this phase, we also conducted a mapping of key stakeholders (D5.3). This phase also involved the establishment of a strong online presence and the creation of promotional materials to generate awareness and interest of the SHORE project, ocean literacy, the EU Mission Ocean & Waters, the Network of European Blue Schools, and the launch of the first open call.

Subsequently, each of the three sub-phases, corresponding to the open calls (M6-M33), are focusing on specific communication and dissemination activities tailored to the unique characteristics of each call. For each open call, we will launch communication and dissemination campaigns in line with the major stages of the call:

- Call launch and submission of projects;
- Evaluation and selection of the blue projects;
- Third-party sub-grant agreement preparation and signature;
- School projects implementation and reporting.

Our strategy around communication and dissemination activities across the three calls in the project involves an ongoing and adaptive approach to maximise effectiveness and engagement:

- **First Call (M6-M19):** The initial call set the foundation for communication strategies. During the first call, communication efforts focused on creating awareness about the project, the goals of the open call, and the benefits of participation. Dissemination materials were tailored to attract diverse schools interested in ocean and river awareness projects. Feedback and engagement from the first call led to adjustments to our communication strategies for the other open calls.
- **Second Call (M14-M24):** Building on the lessons learned from the first call, the second call benefits from refined communication approaches. The dissemination strategy was adapted based on the response and participation patterns observed in the first call. Communication materials were adjusted to address specific challenges and highlight successful outcomes from the first

blue projects. Continuous engagement with stakeholders ensures that the project remains visible and relevant. This is the current phase.

- **Third Call (2nd quarter of 2025 – 1st quarter of 2026):** By the time of the third call, the communication and dissemination activities will have undergone further refinement. Insights gained from the first two calls will contribute to a more targeted approach. The communication will also be tailored around success stories, impact assessments, and best practices from earlier phases to encourage participation in the final call.

The final phase (M33-M36) will concentrate on the presentation of project results, impact assessment, and the dissemination of comprehensive reports on the outcome of the open calls. Communication and dissemination efforts during this stage will highlight success stories, lessons learned, and best practices, contributing to the legacy of the project and fostering a sense of community among participating schools. This phase also includes the drafting of the final report on communication, dissemination, and outreach (M34).

Overall, this phased approach ensures that communication and dissemination activities are strategically integrated into the project timeline, maximising their effectiveness and impact throughout the entire duration of the SHORE project.

2.2. Objectives

The **main objective of the communication and dissemination activities** is to maximise the impact of the project by:

- **building widespread awareness about the project**, its goals, and the importance of ocean and river literacy among the target audiences, including schools, students, educators, and local communities.
- **giving a "sense of excitement" for individuals** to understand the importance of the ocean to their lives and realise how their individual actions affect the marine environment with community activities, exhibitions, school projects, and online interaction platforms.
- **highlighting and showcasing the successful outcomes** of the blue projects implemented by the schools. Share success stories, best practices, and lessons learned to inspire and guide other schools and communities interested in similar initiatives.
- **showing how European collaboration has achieved more** than would have otherwise been possible, notably in fostering citizen engagement through a project-based approach and contributing to solving societal and environmental challenges.
- **making better use of results**, by ensuring they are taken up by decision-makers to influence policy-making and ensure a follow-up of the development of specific policies related to ocean and river literacy.
- **fostering a sense of community** among participating schools through the twinning mechanisms and the Network of European Blue Schools, and

stakeholders through the Mission Oceans Helix and other engagement activities. Facilitate communication channels that allow for the exchange of ideas, collaboration, and ongoing support even after the project's conclusion, contributing to a lasting network focused on ocean and river literacy.

2.3. Target groups

The consortium has identified several target groups that have an interest in the SHORE project and will use our results. These are being targeted by different communication and dissemination actions, as well as networking and clustering activities, as detailed in the table below.

Targeted audiences will be refined throughout the lifetime of the project in relation to the various activities developed within the different work packages.

Target audiences differ from stakeholders' categories which are groups of individuals who may be affected by or may influence the project. An analysis of SHORE's stakeholders was performed and reported in deliverable D5.3 "Stakeholders Engagement Report". Some key information on the different categories and the analysis is summarised in section 4 of this document.

The table below presents the target groups that will best make use of the project's results.

Table 1: Target groups, objectives, and channels for communication and dissemination

Target groups	Description/Role	Objectives	Content & Channels
School Ecosystem (Students, Staff, Teachers, Families)	This is the main target of the project. They have a direct interest in all of SHORE's activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise their awareness on ocean and water literacy - Inform them about SHORE's teaching materials - Promote the NEBS - Get them to apply for the grants and implement blue projects 	Website, Social media, Newsletters, Videos, Print materials, Workshops, Trainings, Popularisation events, Direct contacts
Local and regional communities (Local associations, and NGOs, Citizens, local authorities)	This target group will act as an amplifier and multiplier.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise their awareness on ocean literacy - Inform them about SHORE's grants for schools - Get them to share our main messages within their communities 	Website, Social media, Newsletters, Videos, Print materials, Popularisation events, Direct contacts
National government		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Garner support and endorsement for 	Direct contact, Official Meetings and

agencies and International organisations	This target group comprises governmental bodies and international organisations (Environmental Ministries, UNESCO, etc.) with a vested interest in environmental and educational initiatives. This target group will act as an amplifier and multiplier.	SHORE's project and blue project initiatives	presentations, Collaborative Government and international agency portals events, and
European and international projects and initiatives	This target group involves organisations, projects, and funding bodies at the European and international levels, with a focus on supporting initiatives related to ocean literacy, blue economy, and sustainability. This target group involves SHORE's sister projects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribute to and participate in collaborative efforts to enhance global ocean literacy - Create synergies with other blue projects and initiatives 	Website, Social media, Newsletters, Videos, Print materials, Mission Oceans Helix, Clustering activities
Media	This target group serves as a crucial channel for disseminating information to a wider audience. This target group plays a large role in shaping public opinion and raising awareness.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase media coverage on ocean literacy and SHORE's activities - Encourage media outlets to feature SHORE's activities and campaigns. 	Website, Social media, Press releases, Direct contacts
General public	This broad target group comprises all civil society actors and general public that are not already included in the other groups (e.g., citizens in other countries).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise their awareness on ocean and water literacy 	Website, Social media, Videos, Print materials, Newsletters, Participation in events,

2.4. SHORE messages

The SHORE communication, dissemination, and outreach activities are tailored to ensure that important messages reach our targeted audiences, and that the public at large connects with SHORE.

For each different audience identified, a distinct strategy using targeted messages, means and language is being used. For each audience, we are trying to answer the following questions and adapt the message we are delivering:

- Why do they need to know?
- What makes the issue urgent?
- What are the consequences if no action is taken?
- What solutions are we offering?
- How does our work relate to their everyday life?
- Does it link to any broader societal issue?

These are some of the **key messages** that we are delivering through the communication and dissemination activities:

- **It is imperative to expand our knowledge about the ocean and rivers in Europe through the Mission Ocean:** Communicate on the importance of expanding knowledge about the ocean and rivers underscores the critical role these ecosystems play and encourage a deeper understanding of the ecological significance among the target audience, fostering a sense of responsibility for their preservation.
- **Engaging schools and fostering awareness among children and the younger demographic is key to a sustainable future:** Recognise the younger generation as key stakeholders and empower them to become advocates for sustainable practices and conservation efforts.
- **Communities play a vital role in supporting the blue transition:** Acknowledge the crucial role of communities and encourage active community participation, fostering a sense of ownership and cooperation in addressing ocean and river literacy.
- **SHORE offers grants to support local initiatives:** Highlight the availability of grants as tangible support for implementing projects and as an incentive for schools to actively participate.
- **SHORE provides tools and materials for the effective implementation of blue projects:** Provide practical tools and materials that will support the effective planning and execution of their projects.
- **Participating schools have the opportunity to become the "Ocean Ambassador of the Year":** Motivate schools and individuals to excel in their initiatives, creating a sense of achievement and recognition within the project community.
- **Blue projects will contribute to a more sustainable and environmentally conscious society:** Encourage participants to view their contributions as part of a broader legacy and stressing the lasting effects, instilling a sense of responsibility for the well-being of the oceans and rivers among current and future generations.

3. Tools, materials, and activities

To reach the objectives of the SHORE project and ensure proper visibility and impact among its target audiences, different tools, materials, and activities are planned throughout the lifetime of the project. They are detailed in this section and summarised in the table below.

Table 2: Summary of the main elements of the SHORE communication and dissemination strategy

Main elements	Description
Visual identity	The project branding includes a project logo , visual identity (including fonts and colours), and templates for Word and PowerPoint.
Communication materials	A communication package containing the main elements of the project is already available and includes: flyer, posters, roll-up banner, and a one-page project description. 1 final brochure , 1 infographic , motion design videos , and partners and schools interviews will also be produced over the course of the project.
Website	The public website contains information targeted for the schools (information about the open calls, the country hubs, the different platforms, trainings for the teachers), as well as specific information targeted towards the different types of stakeholders linked to the project. Generic information about the project is also included for the general public.
Social networks and online presence	Social media accounts (1 LinkedIn page, 1 Facebook page, 1 Instagram account, and 1 Twitter account) were created to reach a wide audience.
Newsletters	6 newsletters sharing news from the project and funded schools, as well as news related to ocean literacy and the NEBS.
Press Relations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 press releases ○ 1 final media press kit ○ 2 articles in specialised magazines ○ Public relations and media coverage (local/national/European press).
Awareness-raising campaigns	Campaigns to raise awareness about the three open calls, the NEBS and Mission Ocean, as well as ocean and water literacy.
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ At least 1 participation in a science popularisation event (e.g., European Researchers' Night) ○ 2 Mission Oceans Nights ○ 1 Ocean Conference and Exhibition ○ 1 Open InfoDay and conference targeting a wide range of stakeholders ○ Organisation of several events: training schools, workshops, webinars for teachers and educators

Stakeholders' engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Mapping of stakeholders ○ A community called Mission Oceans Helix to drive impact, exploitation, and dissemination activities. ○ Stakeholders' engagement through workshops, in-person meetings, etc.
Networking clustering	and Synergies with relevant EU projects and initiatives

The tools, social media accounts, and project website are developed and managed by Euronovia with inputs from the partners. They are all available for translations in the country hubs' languages to ensure the best dissemination at the local level. The tools are all downloadable through the internal project management platform. In addition, public materials are available for download on the project website. Other activities are implemented by all partners with support from Euronovia as WP5 leader.

3.1. Visual identity

The project branding, created right at the start of the project, is helping all partners to communicate about the project in a uniform, consistent, and professional manner. It includes the project logo, project identity, and templates for Word and PowerPoint documents.

Figure 1: SHORE logotype – Vertical version

The **SHORE logotype** consists of a sphere representing the environment as a main shape. The upper part depicts the sky illuminated by the sun as a symbol of the leadership that lights a path to the future, through education and ocean literacy. The three colours used for the water symbolise the three bodies of water addressed in the project: oceans, rivers, and seas.

The main font is a rounded sans serif typeface which matches well with the isologo and gives a sense of fluidity, connecting with the general concept of water. The original font was modified to make the H look like books on a shelf, as a symbol of education, and the E like a door to the future.

This logo is being used in all communications (tools, deliverables, presentations, invitations etc.) to ensure a good recognition of the project. Specific guidelines on how to use the logo both on a white and dark background, as well as indications on its placement, font and colours are described in its **brand manual** (available to the EC upon request).

Figure 2: Extract from the SHORE Brand Manual

The different versions of the project logo, as well as the brand manual, are available for download on the project management platform.

Templates for the project deliverables, meeting agenda and minutes were also created, together with a PowerPoint template to be used by the partners for all presentations about SHORE, both in internal and external events. Following new indications from the Mission Ocean & Waters, the templates were updated with the Mission's graphical elements.

Figure 3: SHORE's Word and PPT templates

3.2. One page project description

A one-page project description was created for distribution to participants in any project-related activity. This document contains a simple description of the SHORE project and its objectives. The design follows the SHORE visual identity and is consistent with the other communication materials developed within the communication package. It is available for download on the project website. To avoid

duplicating tools and reducing the environmental footprint of the project, it was decided that this document would mostly be aimed for online distribution (as a first introduction to the project), while the brochure (which has more detailed information) is distributed during events.

Figure 4: SHORE's One-page project description

3.3. Brochures

A first project **brochure** with general information on the project and the open calls was created and distributed to partners for use at any external events that the consortium is organising or attending. It is also available for download on the project website in different languages (Estonian, German, Hungarian, Italian, Romanian, Turkish, and Ukrainian).

Figure 5: Cover and back pages of the SHORE brochure

A **final brochure** will also be developed by Euronovia towards the end of the project to present the main achievements of SHORE. It will be widely distributed through the project contact database, the website, social networks, and during the final openfoday and conference at the end of the project.

3.4. Roll-up and Posters

A **roll-up banner** was created using the project's visual identity and the same graphical elements used in other communication tools. The text content of the roll-up was kept to a minimum as its main functions is the easy recognition of the project during events. This banner is being during internal and external events attended by the consortium to promote and present the project.

It is also available for download on the project website in different languages (Estonian, German, Hungarian, Italian, Romanian, Turkish, and Ukrainian).

Figure 6: The SHORE roll-up banner

Two posters were produced: one for the project partners to print and use during events, and the other one for the schools who receive grants from the project to display it in their classrooms and highlight their participation in the project. Both posters are available on the SHORE website in different languages (Estonian, German, Hungarian, Italian, Romanian, Turkish, and Ukrainian).

Figure 7: SHORE's posters for partners and for schools

3.5. Infographics

A set of infographics will be produced during the course of the project. Several options will be considered for their content depending on the needs of the partners. The focus could be on key facts on ocean and water literacy, best practices guides, etc.

3.6. Website

The project website (<https://shoreproject.eu>) is of crucial importance to enhance the visibility of SHORE as it serves as the main communication tool for the wide dissemination of the project activities, materials, deliverables, and outcomes.

Together with SHORE's social media accounts, the website is a key tool for reaching out to a wide audience, communicate about the project and its results. The website provides essential information on the project, such as its objectives, the grants for schools, resources available, etc. The SHORE website also acts as a central point to reach the different platforms in use by the project (Submission platform, Community platform, Mission Ocean Helix).

The website was launched in November 2023 (M4). Since June 2024, it also offers several accessibility tools: it is now possible to increase or decrease the size of the text, apply grayscale or higher contrast, and more options. This feature is visible on the left-hand side of the screen where a blue square with a person is visible. This was an important update to ensure the accessibility of our website to every user.

Figure 8: Homepage of the SHORE website

The SHORE website is kept regularly updated, with new content regarding the open calls, events, deliverables, and other resources. An additional page “Learn about related projects” was added to the website in order to present our sister projects and other Mission projects. News articles are regularly published with the latest information about the project activities, thanks to inputs from all project partners. At M17, **20 news articles** have already been published.

In addition, SHORE partners are all regularly publishing news articles about the project and its activities through their institutional website.

Analytics

The impact of the website is monitored using Google Analytics. In the period from November 2023 to November 2024, the website was visited by 18,470 visitors with 59,413 page views.

Figure 9: Overview of the SHORE website visitors over time

The most visited pages are the Open calls page, followed by the homepage, and the page about the project itself. This shows that the important efforts made in terms of communication to promote the Open calls are very fruitful and contribute to make it visible. Clear spikes in visits can be seen during the open call application periods (February – March, and September–November), as well as during the announcement of the first open call results (June 2024).

3.7. Social media

Social media are being used by the consortium to inform and connect with our different target groups, including educators, policymakers, and the scientific community, as well as to reach out to the general public (students, citizens, local communities). They are also a key tool to communicate about the Mission Ocean and Waters, its objectives and activities (charter, service portal, other funded projects, etc.).

At the start of the project, four social media accounts were opened for SHORE: **a LinkedIn page, a Twitter account, a Facebook page, and an Instagram account**. These four platforms each have their specificities and their own userbase, which allows us to reach a variety of audiences, in line with our target groups.

- **LinkedIn:** This is currently the main platform for European projects and allows us to connect with professionals in relevant fields, as well as the whole EU ecosystem.
- **X/Twitter:** This platform is used by European projects and by researchers, and policy-makers. Due to current instability with the platform and its lack of moderation, Euronovia is closely monitoring the evolution of the situation and is considering archiving the SHORE account and potentially move to another platform (e.g., Bluesky).
- **Instagram:** Through this platform, we are reaching a wide audience, including the younger generation.
- **Facebook:** This platform allows us to reach our target within the school ecosystem (teachers, staff, etc.) and the general public

The four accounts are managed by Euronovia. Partners regularly contribute by sharing news with them and posting through their institutional accounts, as well as personal ones. We are thus able to reach further than the project's followers and use the extensive networks of all partners. Social media templates (text and visuals) are regularly developed by Euronovia and offered to the partners for specific campaigns. This facilitates the work of the partners and maximise the visibility of the project through harmonised designs.

Euronovia and the SHORE partners also ensure wider dissemination on social media by following and tagging relevant organisations, projects, and other initiatives related to our topics (e.g., Mission Ocean & Waters, EMSEA, , etc.), as well as relevant hashtags (e.g., #MissionOcean, #OceanLiteracy #BlueEconomy #EU4Ocean).

Figure 10: SHORE's LinkedIn and Instagram accounts

Figure 11: SHORE's Facebook and Twitter/X accounts

At M17, the SHORE accounts have the following number of followers:

- LinkedIn (@shore-community): 807 followers
- Instagram (@shore.school.community): 710 followers
- Facebook (SHORE-Community): 290 followers
- X/Twitter (@shore_community): 274 followers

The KPI for our social media was to reach 500 followers in total. This target has been reached very early on and we are striving to keep going beyond our initial target and reach more and more people.

A YouTube channel was created to share audiovisual materials (see section 3.8).

The impact of the SHORE social media channels is regularly monitored through the platforms' statistics tools to evaluate the best performing posts.

At M17:

- On LinkedIn, the best performing post with 2,713 impressions and 619 clicks was about the Wave of Change conference organised by our SHORE coordinator YTU. The second was the 2nd Consortium meeting with 1,856 impressions. And the third is the announcement of the results of the 1st SHORE Open Call with a total of 1,801 impressions and 106 clicks.
- On Instagram, our 4 best performing posts are related to the funded schools, with a combined total of 2,114 impressions and 129 interactions.
- On Facebook, the best performing boost is the post that Euronovia boosted on the 2nd Open Call, with 44,101 impressions and 387 interactions.
- On X/Twitter, as of June 2024, Twitter Analytics is no longer available for free which limits our evaluation.

Lastly, specific awareness-raising campaigns are being organised and shared on social media, see section 5 for further information.

3.8. Audio-visual materials & YouTube channel

Different types of audio-visual materials are planned during the project duration and will be published on the [SHORE YouTube channel](#).

Figure 12: Homepage of the SHORE YouTube channel

The following audio-visual materials will be produced and published on YouTube:

- **Motion design videos** to present the project objectives and activities in an attractive and dynamic way (by Euronovia around mid-term)
- **Interviews of schools and partners** are being recorded and edited for online publication. It will include interviews in several languages with subtitles to ensure a good representation of the diversity of the schools.
- **Webinars** organised by the project and recorded for public dissemination
- Any additional audio-visual content from the partners or the schools

Results: At M17, the following videos have been published (on YouTube or on social media account):

- A [summary video](#) of the Wave of Change conference organised by YTU in Istanbul
- A [summary video](#) of Mission Ocean & Waters Night
- A summary video of the Consortium Meeting in Venice
- 5 Interviews of the partners
- 5 recordings of SHORE webinars

A series of **motion-design videos** are being developed by Euronovia, with the support of the partners, to encourage the younger generation to become agents of change, one of the key messages of the SHORE project. In addition, to promoting SHORE and the EU Mission, these videos will aim to show students (and by extension, their teachers) how they can take action for the protection of our ocean and waters. They will be fully in line with the Mission Ocean & Waters' objectives and will strongly support the communication and dissemination activities of the project. These videos will be published on the SHORE YouTube channel in the first quarter of 2025. They will also be made available to any schools, teachers, or parents wishing to use them to educate children.

3.9. Publications

3.9.1. Newsletters & mailings

A total of **6 newsletters** (twice a year) are planned to be sent out to the newsletter subscribers during the duration of the project. Newsletters are made available on the project website (<https://shoreproject.eu/newsletter/>) and disseminated on social media.

A [subscription form](#) for the SHORE newsletter was created at M1 in order to constitute early on a sufficient list of subscribers. At M17, the newsletter has 173 subscribers and the objective is to reach at least **250 subscribers** by the end of the project.

The newsletter comprises news from the project and funded schools, as well as news related to ocean literacy, Mission Ocean, and the NEBS.

Additional mailings are also being sent out to the subscribers lists (in line with the GDPR) depending on the needs of the project.

Results: At M17, the following newsletters and mailings have been published:

- [Newsletter #1: February 2024](#)
- [Newsletter #2: September 2024](#)
- [Mailing "Launch of Open Call #2": September 2024](#)

3.9.2. Deliverables

All deliverables are accessible through the project's website, with the level of dissemination determining the extent of public availability (Public or Sensitive). In cases where a deliverable is categorised as "sensitive", a condensed yet informative publishable summary is provided on the SHORE website. This approach ensures transparency while respecting confidentiality concerns. The same process will be followed for all new deliverables.

3.9.3. Scientific publications

SHORE is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project. As such, the communication and dissemination activities are not specifically designed for the dissemination of research publications. However, several academic institutions are involved in the project and intend to share some results from the project through scientific publications

Scientific journals identified by the partners for publication include, but are not limited to: Marine Pollution Bulletin, Frontiers in Marine Science, Environmental Education Research, and Education Sciences.

SHORE publications are stored in the [SHORE Zenodo Community](#) and follow open access rules as described in section 1.1.4.

At M17, the partners have published the following:

5 Conference proceedings:

- Çetinkaya, Afşin, and Başhan Veysi. 'Exploring Sustainable Strategies for Oceanic Development: A Blue Growth Perspective'. Zenodo, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.35208/ert.1478089>.
- Çetinkaya, Afşin. 'Advancing water literacy: Integrating knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors for sustainable management in the face of climate change'. Zenodo, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14038067>.
- Elif Can, Cengiz, Üçüncüoğlu Cevat, and Bozkurt Refik. 'Promoting ocean literacy via blue schools in Europe'. Zenodo, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14038075>.
- Cevat, Ucuncuoğlu, Cengiz Elif Can, and Bozkurt Refik. 'Exploring public perceptions: ocean literacy and climate change in Europe'. Zenodo, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14038081>.
- Melotti, Luca, Sarah Currò, Jean-Marie Graïc, Andreea Ionaşcu, and Marian Paiu. 'SHORE: Empower Students as the Agents of Change'. In Abstract Book of the 35th ECS Conference. Zenodo, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14516859>.

3.10. Press Relations

Specific efforts will be dedicated to press relations in order to ensure a good media coverage about the SHORE project at local, national, and European levels. A [specific page](#) on the SHORE website was also created to gather all content addressed to the press.

At M17, 4 press releases have been published by the project:

- [Press release](#) announcing the opening of the first call for proposals was published in January 2024. It includes key information about the project. A press release template was also shared with the partners so that it could be adapted to local context and translated in various languages.
- [Press release](#) jointly released on 8 June with the sister project ProBleu on the occasion of World Ocean Day. It aimed to highlight the importance of ocean and water literacy in school communities.
- [Press release](#) jointly released with the sister projects ProBleu and BlueLightS on 16 September to announce the upcoming open calls for the three projects.
- [Press release](#) announcing the launch of the second open call was published on 18 September 2024.

All press releases are available on the [Press Room page](#) of the SHORE website.

Upcoming:

- A **press release** will be published for the launch of the third open call
- A **final media press kit** will be prepared at the end of the project for massive dissemination of the project final outcomes.
- Additional press releases may be produced depending on the needs of the partners.

At least **2 articles in specialised magazines**, including magazines for children, are expected by the end of the project.

At M17, at least **19 media appearances** were recorded in online and print media, including radio and TV broadcasts. The list of media appearances is available upon request.

3.11. Events

3.11.1. Organisation of events

As part of the project activities, the SHORE partners are organising several types of events for communication, dissemination, and outreach purposes.

Below is a list of high-level events that will be organised over the course of the project:

- A **launch event** for Mission Ocean Helix organised by Crowdhelix and supported by all SHORE partners, the Helix event will be the 1st of the **3 Stakeholders**

Workshops organised throughout the project and designed to promote knowledge sharing, collaboration and the blue transition pathway. The stakeholder workshops, which will be online and registered on the EventBrite platform, will involve and reach out to relevant stakeholders of the SHORE project and involve them in the Blue Transition.

- An **Ocean Conference and Exhibition** will be organised by YTU (M22-M34) to raise awareness of the rising danger of environmental and climate challenges relevant to the Mission Oceans.
- An **Open infoday and conference** targeted to a wide range of stakeholders. Several options are being considered by the consortium for this event.
- Two **Mission Ocean & Waters Nights** will be held simultaneously by YTU, UNIPD, WSB Akademia, and MARE NOSTRUM in 2024 and 2025. It will raise awareness of the ways researchers contribute to our daily life by conducting research and making innovations that improve our life and their crucial role for society. These events are organised as part of WP3.
- Four **Clustering events** to interact and cooperate with other EU-funded projects and existing initiatives (e.g., Youth4Ocean, EMSEA, ProBleu, BlueLightS, etc.)
- Two **webinars** on the project results (years 2–3) to cover a larger audience using web tools

At M17, 5 webinars and 2 high-level events have been organised by the consortium:

- SHORE webinar “Mare Incognitum: (What) do we learn about the sea in school?” | 6 December 2023
- SHORE Webinar: Delve into SHORE's first open call for schools | 27 February 2024
- SHORE Webinar: Ocean Literacy - Journey to the Depths | 15 March 2024
- SHORE Open Call #2 – Info Webinar | 16 October 2024
- Let's talk about the Baltic | 4 December 2024
- Wave of Change conference organised by YTU in Istanbul on 14 May 2024
- The first edition of **Mission Ocean & Water Night** was simultaneously organised in Turkey, Italy, Poland and Romania on 7 June 2024 (one day ahead of World Ocean Day) as part of WP3 activities. Communication for this event was supported by Euronovia (posters, social media, announcements, summary video, etc.). This successful collaboration will be repeated for the second edition in 2025.

Figure 13: Summary video of Mission Ocean & Waters Night published on Instagram

The partners, and specifically the country hubs, have also organised several local events to raise the awareness of and engage local communities and several are planned for the second half of the project. Under WP3, each Country Hub is organising at least **four community activities** (e.g., workshop, webinar, symposium, meetNtalk, etc.) per open call period to increase the awareness of the public and involve the community in ocean issues. Detailed information are available in deliverable 3.1.

Additional events will be organised depending on local needs and opportunities.

3.11.2. Participation in external events

Over the course of the project, partners are expected to take part in several events in order to promote SHORE, the open calls, the NEBS, and disseminate the outcomes of the project. Below is a preliminary list of events divided into three categories. This list is kept regularly updated by all project partners through a shared Excel file on the project’s document repository.

Table 3: List of relevant events to target for SHORE partners

Popularisation events				
Name	Date	Location	Partner planning to attend	
Green Week 2025 & 2026	Spring Yearly	- Any location	TBC	
European Night Researchers'	September Yearly	- Any location	UNIPD, WSB	

Conferences, Fairs, etc.					
Name	Date	Location	Partner planning to attend		
European Ocean Days/Mission Ocean & Waters Annual Forum)	3-7 March 2025	Brussels/Online	Euronovia, YTU		
European Geosciences Union - EGU Annual Assembly	27 April - 2 May 2025	Vienna, Austria	KUW		
European Maritime Day	21-23 May 2025	Cork, Ireland	Euronovia		
UN Ocean Conference	9-13 June 2025	Nice, France	TBC		
DOORS Stakeholders Conference	May 2025 (TBC)	TBC	Mare Nostrum		
Black Sea Common Maritime Agenda Stakeholder Conference	Dates TBC	TBC	Mare Nostrum		
European Marine Science Educators Association (EMSEA) Annual Conference	2025 & 2026	TBC	TBC		
European Science Engagement Association (EUSEA) Annual Conference 2025	14-15 May 2025	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	TBC		
European Maritime Day 2026	2026	Limassol, Cyprus	TBC		
European Ocean Days/Mission Ocean & Waters Annual Forum 2026	2026	TBC	TBC		
European Citizen Science Conference 2026	2026	TBC	TBC		
European Science Engagement Association (EUSEA) Annual Conference 2026	2026	TBC	TBC		

At M17, partners have participated in **26 conferences** (including presentations, posters, and workshops), **6 webinars**, and **2 popularisation events**.

Among these, we would like to highlight the following:

- Organisation of a satellite event with sister projects ProBleu and BlueLightS at the **UN Ocean Decade Conference** on 8 April 2024 in Barcelona by YTU
- Presentation and Participation in the **Black Sea Stakeholders Conference** on 11 September 2024 in Chisinau, Moldova by YTU and Mare Nostrum
- Presentation at the **EU Blue Schools Webinar: Navigating Funding for Blue Schools** on 9 October 2024 by F6S
- Organisation of a session, as well as several presentations and posters at the **MARBLUE Conference** on 23-25 October in Constanta, Romania by Mare Nostrum, YTU and EU&Pro

The full list of events is available upon request.

Euronovia and all partners will keep monitoring the conferences and other events to ensure a wide participation and dissemination of the project results.

3.12. Mission Ocean & Waters Helix

The SHORE consortium has developed a community called the [Mission Ocean & Waters Helix](#) on [CrowdHelix's](#) custom-built AI-powered platform to drive impact, exploitation, and dissemination activities. The Helix was set up on the CrowdHelix platform at M6 of the project and is acting as a resource tool with links to the website, social media, and any dissemination and communication tools produced during the project.

Supported by the CrowdHelix network of over 700 organisations from 56 countries and more than 13,000 researchers, the **Mission Ocean & Waters Helix aims to involve more than 250 organisations from academia, education and training in the blue economy, water and marine ecosystems, and related fields**. Policy-makers, civil society organisations, and public administrations will also be invited to join the Helix. This diversity of stakeholders will cover all aspects of the project and ensure continued interest from key stakeholders during and after the project.

Helix members will have access to the following key features:

- Publish collaboration opportunities and results;
- Offer their expertise;
- Interact with experts and other organisations;
- Promote events and educational events aiming at the visibility of the action.

The Helix represents a key tool to communicate about the Mission Ocean & Waters, its objectives, and activities within the Community. The Mission Ocean & Waters Helix provides a direct link to the Mission Ocean and Waters service portal within the resources section. The Helix will disseminate relevant information from the Mission Ocean portal to its members, including the posting of opportunities about the

initiatives, tools, resources, and financing options released in the portal and dedicated to successful engagement in ocean and water conservation efforts.

The Crowdfunder platform also has a unique feature that increases the chances of finding relevant partners, thereby increasing the value of both the Helix and the organisations registered within it. The platform runs a matchmaking algorithm (recommender engine) that matches posted opportunities with researchers and institutions that have the required expertise or infrastructure. Once an organisation or individual researcher signs up to the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix and profiles their expertise, the platform's recommender engine will help the Crowdfunder team match their expertise to suitable opportunities within the Helix.

Mission Ocean & Waters Helix will be established on the broader Crowdfunder platform and hosted alongside the other thematic communities available on the platform (Water, Black Sea, Citizen Science, Open Science...) where it can cross-fertilise opportunities with other relevant Horizon Europe themes.

Finally, once new members join the Helix, they will be able to participate in the **two Mission Ocean & Waters Helix events, as well as six online events including stakeholder engagement activities** that will be organised during the lifetime of the SHORE project. All these features will facilitate collaborative partnerships between Mission Ocean stakeholders and researchers in Europe and beyond, leading to a self-sustaining community that will remain active after the project ends.

An open innovation community, such as the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix, can play a pivotal role in advancing the project's purpose of raising awareness of ocean literacy and empowering students as agents of change. By bringing together experts from diverse fields related to marine science, conservation, and education, the Helix serves as a collaborative platform to address complex challenges facing our oceans. Through collaborative problem-solving, knowledge sharing, and resource pooling, the community facilitates the development of innovative solutions that can contribute to the broader mission of promoting ocean literacy in society.

The Helix provides a unique networking opportunity for educators, researchers, and advocates focused on ocean literacy. This collaborative environment fosters the exchange of best practices in education, enabling educators to access shared resources and innovative teaching methodologies. Through the community's collective influence, there is potential to contribute to shaping educational policies and standards that prioritise ocean literacy, creating a positive impact on students and society at large. The Helix not only aims to accelerate the pace of innovation in marine science but also extends its reach to educational initiatives that empower students to become informed and proactive stewards of the oceans.

Moreover, the [Mission Ocean & Waters Helix](#) serves as a catalyst for increased visibility and awareness around the importance of ocean literacy. By connecting experts with educators, students, and other stakeholders, the community amplifies efforts to raise awareness and inspire action.

Mission Ocean & Waters

Increasing the awareness of ocean literacy among society, with a specific focus on empowering students as agents of change

[Leave](#)

[View Opportunities](#)

Background

The Blue Economy, which encompasses economic activities related to oceans, seas and coasts, is vital to life on Earth. However, the rapid degradation of marine and freshwater ecosystems poses challenges that threaten the well-being of European citizens. This underlines the urgency outlined in the EU Green Deal and the Mission "Restore Our Ocean and Waters" by 2030.

Challenges remain in promoting ocean literacy, especially among young people, as marine ecosystems face increasing threats. Deliberative democracy, social innovation, citizen science and awareness-raising campaigns are key tools. Recognising youth as catalysts for change, initiatives should integrate life-changing projects into school curricula and promote grassroots and international mobilisation. Communities need to be empowered with knowledge that fosters an understanding of the importance of the ocean and individual impacts on the marine environment.

The evolving concept of environmental education emphasises a holistic approach to sustainable development. Coordination, engagement at local and international levels, and mobilisation across all sectors are essential for a 'Decade of Action' to achieve the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals. Despite progress, a comprehensive approach to the challenges remains crucial.

Key Project

Empower Students as the Agents of Change (SHORE) is a 36-month HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions funded by the European Union.

SHORE aims to improve ocean literacy by involving students and teachers in the implementation of Mission Ocean objectives through collaborative projects and activities at the school level. This initiative will develop training materials and educational courses aligned with blue curricula for schools in the Baltic Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Danube and Rhine regions. Participating schools will have the opportunity to apply for grants to support

Seeking collaborators for Mission Ocean & Waters projects?
Post a new Opportunity in this Helix

[Create Post](#)

785 Experts

286 Organisations

50 Countries

EU MISSION RESTORE OUR OCEAN & WATERS BY 2030

2:08

EU Mission Restore our Ocean & Waters

Ivica Ilic
Helix Manager

[Message](#)

Figure 14: Homepage of the Mission Oceans Helix

3.12.1. Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Roles and Protocols

As Task 5.5 Leader, Crowdhelix has the overall responsibility for creating and managing the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix with the support and involvement of all partners. The community aims to profile over 250 relevant organisations from more than 40 countries worldwide by M36. The Helix will include:

- SHORE Consortium members
- Crowdhelix Network members (the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix will be promoted to the existing 13,000+ users)
- Strategically aligned projects and partners
- Policymakers, exploiters and other relevant stakeholders.

All consortium members are involved in the development of the Helix. They are also expected to share the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix with their existing networks and encourage them to join. Crowdhelix is an open innovation platform, meaning that any individual or organisation of any size, anywhere in the world, can request access to the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix, provided they can demonstrate a strategic commitment to collaborative research and innovation.

Crowdhelix is the dedicated **Helix Manager** to oversee the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix. The Helix Manager has an operational role in the management and animation of the Helix backend and is expected to post regularly via the admin panel:

- Events: those relevant to the Helix, open to all members, and led by a project partner or other Crowdhelix member.
- Resources: links to policy documents, key project outputs, and media that may be featured on the page for longer.
- Announcements: any short update and/or link that is suitable to appear at the top of the Helix page for a short period of time.

The Project Coordinator from YTU will be the **leader of the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix**. This honorary and strategic role is usually filled by a researcher who is willing to drive the scientific direction of the Helix. We see being a Helix Leader as an important role that:

- Drives the agenda and scientific direction of the Helix within the Crowdhelix platform.
- Understands the big picture of what the Mission Oceans Helix is doing and how members are working across Europe.
- Works closely with the Crowdhelix team who will provide direct support.

Throughout the execution of the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix activities, the Crowdhelix team will support the Helix Leader in:

- facilitating links with research institution champions, corporations, SMEs and industry;
- adding new champions to the thematic mailing lists and the Crowdhelix platform;
- collecting information from Crowdhelix members as needed.
- assist with promotional activities;
- organising events (prepare agenda, contact speakers, set up an event page, send registration link, promote via Crowdhelix).

Partners are considered as **Helix Champions** and will be encouraged and reminded to share:

- relevant opportunities related to the project outputs,
- new opportunities in the same field.

Helix events and workshops will be designed to generate interest and new opportunities. Organised by Crowdhelix and supported by all SHORE partners, Helix events are designed to encourage knowledge sharing and collaboration. A typical agenda will include short briefs on exploitable results and breakout discussions on emerging topics, closely connected to the topic of the action. The nature and objectives of each Helix event will be determined following the launch of Mission Ocean & Waters Helix. The objectives, format and audiences of the Helix events and stakeholders workshops may vary according to the needs and progress of the project and will be discussed and agreed upon with partners.

Crowdhelix will commit to maintaining the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix for at least 2 years after the end of the project. At the end of the SHORE project, the Helix will continue to be hosted on the Crowdhelix platform, and all those who signed up during the project will be able to keep their accounts for free (as external organisations), as well as have the option for their organisations to join the network as full members.

4. Stakeholders engagement, clustering and networking

Stakeholder engagement is pivotal in Horizon Europe projects, and in particular for Mission Ocean & Waters projects, as it ensures the alignment of research and innovation efforts with societal needs and priorities. Involving stakeholders—ranging from industry partners to policy-makers, civil society, and end-users—enhances the relevance and applicability of project outcomes. It fosters co-creation, enabling diverse perspectives to shape solutions that address real-world challenges. Early and continuous engagement builds trust, facilitates knowledge exchange, and boosts the uptake of results, maximizing impact. Furthermore, it ensures transparency and accountability, which are central to Horizon Europe’s mission of fostering inclusive and sustainable innovation, contributing to Europe’s scientific, social, and economic advancement.

The clustering of initiatives within the project enables collaboration between different stakeholders, including research institutions, NGOs, and industry partners, securing triple, quadruple or quintuple connection between stakeholders. This collaborative approach facilitates the exchange of knowledge, resources, and innovative solutions, thereby increasing the overall impact of the project. In addition, networking activities provide a platform for the project to connect with like-minded organisations, share best practices and explore potential synergies, thereby extending the reach and impact of the SHORE project activities.

The collective efforts of committed stakeholders, clustered collaborations, and extensive networks not only enhance the quality of educational content but will also contribute to a broader societal awareness of the importance of ocean conservation and sustainability. This multi-faceted approach ensures that the project becomes a catalyst for positive change, influencing policy, inspiring action, and fostering a sense of shared responsibility for our oceans.

4.1. Typology of stakeholders to address

Here are some key target stakeholders at national, European, and international levels that will be considered in the SHORE project:

Educational Institutions

- Schools: Primary, secondary, and tertiary institutions can serve as focal points for integrating ocean literacy into the curriculum, fostering awareness from an early age.
- Universities and Marine Science Departments: Higher education institutions contribute to advanced research, training future professionals in environmental/ocean/marine science, and collaborating on innovative projects.

Teachers and Educators

- Teachers from various fields: Play a crucial role in integrating ocean literacy across subjects, ensuring a multidisciplinary approach.
- Environmental Educators: Specialised educators dedicated to promoting awareness and understanding of environmental issues, including those related to oceans.

Governmental and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs):

- Environmental Protection Agencies: Enforce regulations, conduct research, and promote sustainable practices to safeguard marine environments.
- Ministries of Education, Environment, etc.: Shape policies, allocate resources, and integrate ocean literacy into formal education systems.
- Ocean/Marine/Water Conservation NGOs: Actively engage in conservation efforts, advocacy, and education to promote sustainable marine practices.
- Educational and Youth Associations: Involved in supporting and engaging students and young people in relevant social issues/problems.

Scientists and Researchers Community

- Marine Biologists, Oceanographers, Environmental Scientists: Conduct critical research, contribute to scientific understanding, and inform conservation strategies.
- Networks and Associations of Scientists and Researchers: Facilitate collaboration, knowledge exchange, and the dissemination of research findings.

Media and Communication Channels

- Science Communication Platforms: Play a vital role in translating complex scientific concepts into accessible information for the public.
- Educational TV Programs: Utilise visual media to communicate ocean-related knowledge to a broader audience.
- Environmental Blogs and Websites: Provide accessible, continuous information on marine issues, fostering public awareness.

Regional and Local Communities (specifically in the case of the country hubs)

- Community Leaders: Mobilise local support, advocate for sustainable practices, and foster community engagement in ocean conservation.
- Parent-Teacher Associations: Act as bridges between schools and communities, supporting educational initiatives and awareness campaigns.
- Local Environmental Groups: Engage in grassroots efforts, address localised issues, and contribute to broader conservation objectives.
- Climate Movements: Mobilise citizens for environmental causes, promoting community-led initiatives for ocean conservation.

Industry

- Companies with a focus on marine conservation: Implement sustainable practices, invest in conservation projects, and contribute to responsible corporate citizenship.
- Businesses with Corporate Social Responsibility programs: Play a role in funding, supporting educational initiatives, and implementing sustainable business practices.

International Organisations

- UNESCO, IOC, IPCC: Influence global policy, provide platforms for international collaboration, and support initiatives that contribute to ocean conservation on a worldwide scale.

Funding and Grant providers

- European Commission Institutes and implementing agencies: EC agencies and institutes can offer funding and support for projects aligned with environmental education and ocean conservation.
- Foundations supporting environmental education: Contribute financial resources to educational programs promoting ocean literacy.
- Grant providers for educational initiatives: Support initiatives that enhance understanding and awareness of oceans among diverse audiences.

Technology Partners

- Companies providing educational technology solutions: Offer innovative tools and platforms to enhance ocean literacy through technology.
- Online learning platforms and games-based companies: Utilise digital platforms and gamification to make ocean-related content engaging and accessible.

Engaging these types of stakeholders can create a comprehensive network to support and promote ocean literacy among students in various capacities. Further details are given in D5.3.

4.2. Stakeholders Analysis and Engagement

Regarding the **Stakeholders Analysis and Engagement**, in the SHORE project, we will perform a Stakeholders Analysis using the Power-Interest Matrix. This involves the systematic assessment of key stakeholders in the SHORE project and leading to the production of the D5.3 - Stakeholder Engagement Report, due at M6 of the project. This section presents a summary of the stakeholders analysis and engagement.

The Power-Interest matrix is a valuable tool for categorising stakeholders based on their level of power and interest in each activity/project. The process will consist of the following steps:

- **Identifying Stakeholders:** Identifying all the individuals, groups, or entities that have a stake in the project. These stakeholders can be internal or external. A comprehensive list will be compiled with the involvement of all partners and

will be recorded in an online database accessible through the SHORE internal management platform.

- **Assessing Power:** Evaluating the level of power or influence each stakeholder holds over the project or organisation. Considering factors like decision-making authority, financial resources, expertise, and access to key channels. Assignment of each stakeholder a power rating, on a scale from low to high.
- **Assessing Interest:** Determination of the level of interest each stakeholder has in the project's outcomes. Interest can be influenced by factors like personal involvement, financial gain, or the impact of project outcomes on their objectives. Assignment of each stakeholder an interest rating, using a scale from low to high.
- **Plotting on the Matrix:** Creation of a matrix with the power on one axis and interest on the other. Placement of the stakeholder groups on this matrix based on their power and interest ratings. This positioning categorises stakeholders into four quadrants: high power/high interest; high power/low interest; low power/high interest; and low power/low interest.
- **Action Planning:** Once stakeholders are plotted, a tailored strategy for each quadrant will be suggested, agreed and implemented by the consortium partners considering that:
 - High-power/high-interest stakeholders require close collaboration and engagement.
 - High-power/low-interest stakeholders should be kept informed but not overwhelmed.
 - Low-power/high-interest stakeholders may need some level of engagement, and,

Low power/low-interest stakeholders can often be monitored without extensive involvement. As part of the project's proactive communication and dissemination strategy, tailored and versatile approaches will be meticulously designed to meet the unique preferences and needs of diverse stakeholders. These approaches will range from direct, interactive methods such as in-person meetings, workshops, and focus groups to broad-reaching communication channels like newsletters, social media campaigns, and digital platforms. The strategy emphasizes not only information sharing but also fostering genuine, long-lasting relationships built on trust and collaboration.

At the core of this effort is the General Power-Interest Matrix, a pivotal tool in strategically prioritizing stakeholder engagement efforts. By categorizing stakeholders based on their influence and interest, the matrix ensures that resources are deployed where they are most impactful, maximising engagement efficiency. This structured approach is key to building and maintaining positive relationships while pre-emptively identifying and managing potential risks associated with stakeholder dynamics. It enables the project to stay adaptable and focused, ensuring alignment with its overarching goals.

Importantly, stakeholder engagement is not static but evolves throughout the project's lifecycle. The constellation of stakeholders can shift significantly as the project's value chain dynamics change. For instance, early stages might emphasize engagement with the school community, educators, or local groups, while later phases could see a shift in focus to policymakers, industry leaders, or international collaborators. The strategy

accommodates such transitions by maintaining flexibility, identifying emerging stakeholders, and reallocating efforts to address their evolving roles and needs effectively.

This comprehensive, dynamic approach underscores the project's commitment to inclusivity and impact, ensuring all relevant voices are heard and valued while driving the successful dissemination and implementation of outcomes.

Finally, it is important to state that the stakeholder mapping process is not exhaustive, potentially leading to some stakeholders being incompletely represented in the mapping exercise. Additionally, the analysis and mapping procedures are inherently subjective, relying on the perspectives and opinions of stakeholders and collaborating partner teams. Therefore, the resulting maps should not be interpreted as objective portrayals of reality but rather as reflections of the viewpoints and interpretations of relevant actors to the project. While subjectivity is inherent, it is not necessarily a limitation, as the primary objective of the mapping is to gain insights into stakeholders' thoughts, positions, and influence.

4.3. Clustering and Synergies with other projects

The "[Framework for State aid for research and development and innovation](#)" defines clusters as organised entities comprising independent parties such as innovative start-ups, small, medium, and large enterprises, research and knowledge dissemination organisations, non-profit entities, and other relevant economic actors.

The main purpose of clusters is to stimulate innovative activities by promoting the sharing of facilities, the exchange of knowledge and expertise, and by making a significant contribution to knowledge transfer, networking, information, dissemination, and cooperation between the entities within the cluster.

As a coordination and support action part of the EU Mission Ocean and Waters the SHORE project recognises the key role of clustering activities. The project aims not only to maximise its impact by promoting its activities and results, but also to improve the efficiency of its actions and activities by learning from the experiences of other organisations. Therefore, the SHORE consortium places particular emphasis on knowledge sharing and networking, seeking to collaborate with individual organisations and experts, as well as with analogous projects with similar funding structures. This collaborative approach is in line with the project's strategy of using collective expertise and experience to optimise its outcomes.

The SHORE project underlines the importance of interdisciplinary cross-collaboration with other high impact EU-funded projects as a catalyst for effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts. The main objectives of this cross-project collaboration are to explore synergies with sister projects funded under the same call and with other projects of the Mission Ocean that have ocean/water literacy activities, to establish two-way communication and dissemination channels, to promote the development of innovative ideas and approaches, and to promote the formation of future consortia aligned with the key ideas of SHORE, while providing support in resource identification.

The SHORE project is well positioned to support other initiatives from two key angles: through its valuable human resources, represented by the expertise of its exceptional consortium members, and through its communication and dissemination efforts, leveraging its growing community of followers through various online platforms such as social media and the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix.

In terms of clustering methodology, a strategic approach has been adopted to maximise the visibility and impact of the EU Mission Ocean and SHORE project outcomes and events. From the outset, the project has prioritized the identification of relevant EU projects and initiatives to foster meaningful collaboration and amplify collective efforts. This process began early in the project's lifecycle, recognizing that early identification is critical to building an effective, targeted, and sustainable networking strategy.

The research for clustering began with an in-depth exploration of initiatives suggested by consortium partners. Leveraging their extensive expertise and pre-existing networks, SHORE partners provided valuable insights and connections to relevant projects, ensuring a strong foundation for the clustering effort. This step has been complemented by systematic investigations using established platforms and databases, including the CORDIS repository, the PREP4BLUE project resources, and the Mission Ocean and Waters portal. These platforms have proven instrumental in mapping out a comprehensive landscape of potential collaborators and complementary initiatives.

Clustering is not just a technical process but a dynamic one, integral to building synergies across projects that share similar goals. By engaging with these identified projects, SHORE aims to enhance the coherence and impact of its activities while contributing to a broader ecosystem of innovation within the Mission Ocean & Waters framework. This collaborative approach also fosters cross-project learning, allowing for the exchange of best practices, innovative ideas, and joint efforts in tackling shared challenges.

As the project progresses, the clustering methodology will evolve to remain adaptive and inclusive, continually identifying and engaging with new initiatives. This ensures that the networking strategy remains relevant and responsive to the shifting landscape of EU-funded projects and their objectives. The emphasis on proactive and deliberate engagement will not only bolster SHORE's impact but also contribute to the collective success of Mission Ocean & Waters and the EU's broader environmental and societal goals. Through this approach, SHORE is positioned as a vital contributor to the mission, working in harmony with other projects to achieve shared outcomes that benefit all stakeholders.

For each project, the evaluation will consider the overall description of the project objectives and activities, together with any additional information available online, to determine their suitability as potential targets for networking activities and which activities might be more relevant. This assessment process will be reiterated at the commencement of year 3 of the project. Following the mapping exercise mentioned above, the identified projects will be compiled and recorded in an online database accessible through the SHORE internal management platform.

To establish connections with identified projects, SHORE will reach out to the coordinators and communication teams of each project. The initial contact will include a brief introduction along with a presentation outlining SHORE's objectives and potential collaboration opportunities. These opportunities may include profiling projects on SHORE's website, supporting dissemination through social media, featuring projects in newsletters, invitation to join the Mission Oceans Helix community, and organising joint (internal and external) events online and in relevant conferences. The implementation of these opportunities is contingent upon the availability of the projects and mutual needs and agreement.

Collaboration has started with the ProBleu and BlueLightS projects, which focus on four key areas:

1. Cross-communication and promotion: The projects have agreed to promote cross-communication and collaboration between their respective calls, events and outputs. Two joint press releases have already been released as part of this collaboration.
2. Website profiling: SHORE, ProBleu, and BlueLightS have profiled the projects on their respective websites.
3. Participation in SHORE's Mission Ocean & Waters Helix community: This will allow impact to be leveraged and collaboration to be fostered.
4. Organisation of joint events: Internal and external events will be jointly organised and implemented. An example of this collaboration was the joint organisation of a satellite event as part of the UN Ocean Decade Conference in Barcelona.

These activities are reported in the relevant sections of this document.

In addition, the communication and coordination teams of the three sister projects have met several times and established a close communication. A shared folder has been created to facilitate collaboration, including a list of social media channels, a calendar of calls for the three projects to ensure alignment, and a list of potential joint activities and ideas to further explore.

Additional EU projects and initiatives have also supported the promotion of the SHORE project and its open calls (e.g., Scientix, DOORS Black Sea, OTTERS project, OS Together network, WestMED Initiative)

Lastly, SHORE is actively involved in the 'Restore our Oceans and Waters' Mission and participates in the **Mission Ocean Communication Collaborative** Taskforce. Euronovia and Crowdhelix are participating in this taskforce and have already presented different project activities (Helix, open call for schools, call for evaluators) during the monthly meetings. This group represents a great opportunity share information and discuss communication objectives with other projects within the Mission Ocean & Waters. We keep the Mission informed all of the main project activities and results.

WestMED Blue Economy Initiative @WestMedStrat · Oct 25
 📢 Three Funding Calls for Primary and Secondary Schools to help increase #OceanLiteracy!

@pro_bleu, @shore_community and @BlueLights_EU each offer grants to support you in your efforts.

Info on their respective webpages or shorturl.at/TT4fS

If interested, be sure to [Show more](#)

Triple Opportunity for Blue Projects
Three Funding Calls for Primary and Secondary Schools Opening in September!

BlueLightS Grants up to 3 000€ 15 September - 15 November	SHORE Grants up to 10 000€ 18 September - 20 November	ProBleu Three grant categories 2 500€, 5 000€, 7 500€ 20 September - 21 November
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BlueLightS SHORE ProBleu Funded by the European Union

EU Maritime & Fish and CINEA

OTTERS Project 333 abonnés · 1 mois · 🌐

📢 The SHORE is looking for evaluators for their upcoming call for schools to increase #WaterLiteracy and promote #WaterStewardship.

👤 Evaluators need to have:

- A university-level degree
- Good command of English
- Computer skills
- Experience related to at least one of the call's topics: Sea-based activities, sustainable use of water resources, biodiversity, hazardous substances and marine litter, and climate change.

You can apply to become an evaluator here: https://Inkd.in/e6EsV_Qy

Mission Ocean | American University of Armenia | ECSA - European Citizen Science Association | Priscila Doran | Carolina Doran | Bruna Gumiero | Gregory Chahrozian | Angelos Lazoudis | Plastic Pirates – Go Europe!

#MissionOcean #OTTERS #CitizenScience #OceanLiteracy #Sustainability

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Become an evaluator for blue projects
shoreproject.eu

Vous et 16 autres personnes 1 commentaire · 1 republication

Figure 15: Examples of social media posts shared by relevant projects & initiatives

5. Campaigns

All the campaigns are promoted by all partners with the support of Euronovia as WP5 leader.

5.1. Campaigns for the Network of European Blue Schools

The Network of European Blue Schools (NEBS) is “an initiative of EU4Ocean, the European Ocean Coalition that connects diverse organisations, projects and people contributing to ocean literacy and the sustainable management of the ocean.”¹

One of the key objectives of the SHORE project is to expand the Network of European Blue Schools (NEBS). In addition, being a member or aspiring member of the NEBS is an eligibility criteria to apply for the SHORE grants. Promoting the network is a priority for SHORE in order to increase the number of potential applicants to our calls for projects. It is, therefore, important for all partners to ensure that schools are aware of the opportunity and willing to apply to the network. Specific communication campaigns are thus required to support this objective and promote the NEBS.

As part of WP3, with the support of WP5, a dissemination plan was developed in order to increase the number of applications and thus the number of potential applicants to the SHORE call for projects. It includes:

- **Direct e-mail/messages to schools:** As a first step, the Country Hubs, but also the consortium partners who have the right contacts, have reached out to the schools from previous collaborations directly. Then, they have expanded to new schools.
- **Top-down dissemination:** Either ministries or local structures with responsibilities in the educational system (such as inspectorates or directorates) were contacted to disseminate the opportunity of applying to the NEBS.
- **Engaging existing networks & communities of schools/teachers/educators:** There are many already established networks for schools and/or teachers & educators that might have an interest in the topic of Blue Schools. Synergies can be created together with them, in order to engage their members to apply.
- **Website & Social media:** Through the main SHORE platforms and the partners', articles and posts are shared to inform schools and encourage them to apply to the NEBS.
- **Dedicated groups/chats:** Posts could also be made in dedicated groups/chats.

Further information about activities implemented in each Country Hub can be found in deliverable D3.1.

More generally, the NEBS will be disseminated by SHORE partners on every occasion when promoting the project. They will put emphasis on the advantages of the NEBS for the schools and (aspiring) membership as an eligibility criteria for the SHORE open calls. Therefore, the NEBS and open calls campaigns (described below) will be very closely implemented.

¹ https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/theme/ocean-literacy-and-blue-skills/ocean-literacy/network-blue-schools_en

It should be noted that the NEBS has two submission and evaluation periods per year. Our dissemination activities are carried out in accordance with this calendar. At SHORE level, the application calendar will be shared on its website and social media through dedicated posts and visuals.

Figure 16: Example of social media post promoting the NEBS

5.2. Open calls campaigns

SHORE will support 100 schools' projects through 3 open calls for a total budget of 900,000€ (with a maximum of 10,000€ grant per project) for primary and secondary schools. The objective is to increase ocean and water literacy, sustainability, and blue economy knowledge among students to mobilise them as agents of change and ramp up the accreditation of the Network of European Blue Schools.

Promoting the SHORE open calls to all our target groups is one of the main activities of our communication and dissemination activities.

Each open call will follow a similar structure with the following phases:

1. Pre-call opening;
2. Call opening & Submission of proposals;
3. Evaluation period;
4. Preparation and signature of agreement;
5. Implementation of the schools project;
6. Reporting.

Each phase requires specific activities from the partners with different messages to be shared depending on the objectives of the phases. The open call campaign is prepared in close collaboration between Euronovia and F6S to ensure the accuracy of the information. Each partner is then expected to disseminate the campaign through their networks.

The table below presents our strategy for each phase and the activities that are implemented.

Table 4: Dissemination activities per open call phases

#	Phases	Activities	Focus
#1	Pre-call opening	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct emails & contact with schools through the country hubs - Online promotion (website & social media) - Inform relevant networks, projects, and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General information about SHORE - General information about the open calls
#2	Call opening & Submission of proposals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct emails & contact with schools through the country hubs - Online promotion (website & social media) - Press release - Newsletter - Inform relevant networks, projects, and initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specific information about the open calls - Guidelines on how to apply
#3	Evaluation period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited communication about the open calls 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Key numbers (No. of projects submitted, etc.)
#4	Preparation & signature of agreement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited communication about the open calls - Sharing communication materials with the schools (posters, visuals, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Key numbers (No. of projects accepted, etc.)
#5	Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social media (including engaging with the schools) - Contact with the schools to receive news and materials - Sharing communication materials with the schools (posters, visuals, etc.) - Online contest for “Ocean Ambassador of the Year” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School projects’ presentations - Schools content & materials - SHORE digital platform
#6	Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contact with the schools to receive news and materials - Online promotion (website and social media) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Results & best practices from the schools - SHORE digital platform - Ocean Ambassador of the Year

We highlight below the activities implemented in particular for Phase 1, 2, and 5 which are the ones requiring the most actions. At M17, we are in Phase 5 – Implementation for the Open Call #1 and in Phase 3 for the Open Call #2.

Phase 1 - Pre-call opening and Phase 2 - Call opening & Submission period

In addition to the SHORE communication package (see section 3), Euronovia has produced templates and visual materials which were made available to the partners to ensure the easy identification of the project through all channels. The following items were created by Euronovia for Open Call #1 and #2:

- Guidelines documents for open call campaign
- Template for email to contact schools and other interested stakeholders
- Template for social media posts (texts and visual), including a calendar
- Template for Press release for the launch of the call
- Template for news article
- Email signature with the dates of the call

Figure 17: Screenshot of the Guidelines for the Open Call #2 campaign

During the Open Call submissions periods, the activities indicated in Table 4 were implemented (*more information is available in the relevant sections of this document*) and resulted in a high visibility for the project. Due to the active involvement of all partners in the campaign, the Open Calls were widely shared (*see some examples below*).

Figure 18: Social media posts about SHORE Open Calls published by CINEA and Mission Ocean & Waters

For Open Call #2, additional efforts were put towards reaching countries and regions from which less applications were submitted during the first open call. For instance, posts in the languages of these regions were published and two social media posts were boosted on Instagram and Facebook (as these are the main platforms to reach teachers) in the targeted countries.

Phase 5 - Implementation

In this phase, two main activities are taking place: Providing communication materials to the funded schools and Promoting the blue projects. Both activities were done with the collaboration of the SHORE mentors which were assigned to the funded schools. They acted as an intermediary between the schools and Euronovia to facilitate the process and remain the main contact point for the schools.

Providing communication materials with the funded schools: A [Trello Board](#) was created by Euronovia to facilitate access to the communication materials for the schools. In this board, funded schools can find:

- Guidelines document for their communication activities
- Information & Templates for social media posts (texts and visuals)
- Downloadable communication materials
- Template for a press release

All these materials will be updated for the Open Call #2 and #3 funded schools.

Figure 19: Trello Board available to the funded schools

Promoting the blue projects: To support the visibility of the schools’ blue projects, Euronovia has designed the “Funded school series”. With the support of the school’s mentors, Euronovia has collected information and pictures from the funded schools. In this series, alongside a short text, 4 images are published for each project:

- Cover page (Blue project title, school’s name, location, target ear, and a picture)
- Short description and a picture
- Quote from a teacher or educator taking part in the project
- Map with the location of the school

Figure 20: Example of social media post for the "Funded schools series"

5.3. Other campaigns

Throughout the duration of the project, several additional awareness-raising campaigns will be organised, using materials developed by the consortium. They will rely primarily on social media and website content shared through the SHORE accounts to reach a wide audience. The partners will act as relay of information.

The table below presents a preliminary list of awareness-raising campaigns that will be implemented by the project.

Table 5: Description of additional awareness-raising campaigns

Campaign	Description
Mission Oceans and Water Helix	A specific communication campaign will be developed by Crowdhelix and Euronovia to announce the launch of the Helix.
Mission Ocean and Waters objectives	This campaign will share the objectives of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”, namely to “protect and restore the health of our ocean and waters through research and innovation, citizen engagement, and blue investments.” It will also emphasise key content from the Mission (charter, portal, calls, events, etc.)
Key facts about ocean and water literacy	Using the SHORE water literacy curricula produced by the partners, this campaign will focus on sharing key facts about our oceans and waters.
Key facts about regional areas	SHORE covers five regional areas, each with their own specificities and challenges. This campaign will present the regional areas.
International days	Throughout the year, there are a series of United Nations’ International days relevant for SHORE (e.g., World Oceans Days, World Water Day, World Environment Day). Activities will be implemented on these days to increase the visibility of the project to a wide audience.

For all the campaigns listed above, dedicated activities have been implemented by the partners through different channels (social media, web articles, newsletters, events, etc.). Among these, we can highlight the following:

- Series of web articles with key fact about each target region ([Mediterranean Sea](#), [Baltic Sea](#), [Black Sea](#), [Danube River](#), [Rhine River](#))
- Launch of the Mission Ocean & Waters helix with dedicated social media posts and news articles
- Dedicated posts for relevant International Days and in particular for World Ocean Day as the date for Mission Ocean & Waters Night was selected on purpose to be near this international day

SHORE
810 abonnés
6 mois

This morning, SHORE hosted a high-level session for its Mission Ocean & Waters Night with many distinguished speakers. They all highlighted the key role of education to empower our youth to become agents of change.

Local activities are now taking place in Türkiye, Poland, Romania and Italy. See you there! https://lnkd.in/eQT_pYmS

Mission Ocean & Waters Night is held in celebration of #WorldOceanDay 🌊 It aims to foster connections between research and education communities, to engage the public, and to highlight the pivotal role of school projects and ocean science research.

#MissionOceanWatersNight #MissionOcean #OceanLiteracy #BlueEconomy #EU4O

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Mission Ocean Night: Empowering Students through Enhanced Communication - SHORE
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18

EUROPEAN UNION

EU MISSIONS
RESTORE OUR OCEAN & WATERS

Concrete solutions for our greatest challenges

#EUmissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

shoreprojectcommunity

shoreprojectcommunity SHORE is proud to be part of #EUmissions, a European initiative to restore our planet and water through research and innovation, talent empowerment and fair employment.

SHORE is dedicated to supporting #MissionOcean's objectives and the global agenda, local communities and schools through education and training activities.

#EUmissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

Figure 21: LinkedIn post for Mission Ocean & Waters Night and World Ocean Day (left) and an Instagram post highlighting SHORE’s support of Mission Ocean & Waters objectives (right)

6. Monitoring and Impact

6.1. Tracking and monitoring of the actions

The partner leading WP5, Euronovia, is responsible for tracking all the communication and dissemination activities of the partners, and using this information to evaluate their impact. A document composed of 4 different tabs was created at the beginning of the project to gather data related to the activities implemented by each partner, namely:

- **Communication actions:** Partners list and give details about all the communication activities done at the level of their organisation to promote the project;
- **Dissemination activities:** Partners list and give details about their dissemination activities aiming to share the project's results;
- **Scientific publications:** Partners list all their publications (papers, conference proceedings, etc) in which SHORE's research and results are used;
- **Events to target:** Partners regularly list interesting events and conferences relevant for SHORE where participation could be envisaged;

This document was uploaded to the project management platform and all partners are regularly reminded to update it as soon as they are involved in a communication or dissemination action to keep track of all the activities implemented within SHORE. An overview of this document is available in Annex 1.

6.2. Impact assessment

Monitoring the impact of the different dissemination activities involves a systematic collection of data and reporting of information from all partners. This information serves to deliver the final verdict on the success of the communication and dissemination process undertaken by the project.

A detailed communication and dissemination table was created in order to check that all activities are planned and are effectively taking place, integrating Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the impact of each activity. KPIs are a measuring factor for the performance and progress of an activity, message, task, etc. towards its expected impact. Several KPIs were defined for each communication and dissemination activity of the project. They are being used to assess the performance of our activities all along the project duration and potentially re-orientate the dissemination plan if KPIs are not matched, and the expected impact not reached.

Euronovia has performed an evaluation of these KPIs at mid-term (M17) for the release of the updated PCDO (D5.2) and a second evaluation will be performed for the Report on Communication, Dissemination, and Outreach activities (D5.5) which will be submitted at the end of the project (M34). Each KPI receives a grade (according to its percentage of completion) which allows us to check if we are on track with the work plan. Depending on the results, corrective measures may be considered and implemented.

The table presenting all KPIs and the results reached at M17 is available in Annex 2. For this mid-term evaluation, the targets, originally set for the end of the project (M36), were adapted to fit the current month of the project (e.g., if 500 followers are expected by M36, we considered the target at M17 to be 236).

The following scale was used to score each KPI:

- If the results are lower than 50% of the target, the result is considered as Low;
- If the results are lower or equal to 75% but above 50%, the result is considered as Moderate;
- If the results are lower or equal to 100% but above 75%, the result is considered as Good;
- If the results are higher than 100%, the result is considered as High.

Over half of our KPIs received a 'High' score, and over $\frac{3}{4}$ are either 'High' or 'Good' (as reported in Annex 2). The activities are thus well on track with the work plan.

Table 6: Distribution of KPI evaluation scores

Score	High	Good	Moderate	Low
% of KPI	52%	33%	10%	5%

The highest KPIs are related to the number of visits on SHORE website, followers of SHORE's social media accounts, subscribers to the newsletters, Helix's community stakeholders, thus proving the high interest and participation in the project. In addition, several activities implemented by the partners have also gone above the KPIs set for M17 (press releases, participation in popularisation events, organisation of webinars, community activities, scientific publications, newsletters/mailings). These numbers are the results of the collective work and actions of all SHORE partners.

The lower-performing KPIs are related to: (i) the number of poster printed. However, this number is most likely higher as the poster were also shared with the schools (and can be seen in many pictures), but we are not able to track down the number that they printed; (ii) the number of project collaborations. Further efforts will be done to reach the final KPI. In addition, while we did not count them in the project collaboration KPIs, a lot of cross-promotion on social media and websites have been done with other projects, in particular from the Mission Ocean & Waters;

Lastly, the only KPI with a low score is related to the number of printed version of the one-page description document. However, as explained in section 3.2, this was expected as it was decided that this tool would rather be used in its online format, and the brochure favoured for in-person activities in order to avoid duplicating materials and reducing the project's environmental footprint. This KPI will be removed from the final analysis at M34 as it is no longer relevant for the project.

Overall, the project is well on track with its KPIs and corrective measures (as detailed above) have been put in place to reach the ones that are underperforming at M17.

7. Conclusion

The communication and dissemination activities have been carried out in line with the Grant Agreement and the strategy and objectives defined in D5.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination, and Outreach (PCDO). During the first half of the project, under the lead of Euronovia and Crowdhelix, all partners successfully participated in the communication and dissemination of the project activities, and in particular for the two open calls and the various activities surrounding them. At M17, the analysis of the KPIs for the period is very satisfying: the indicators measuring the performance of the communication and dissemination actions are mostly 'high' or 'good', with just a few KPIs behind schedule. Corrective measures have already been put in place. The project benefits from a strong visibility at EU level which ensure the success of its various activities.

A final report on the communication, dissemination and outreach activities of the SHORE project (D5.5) will be published at M34.

8. Annexes

Annex 1 – Overview of the form tracking the partners’ communication and dissemination actions

Communication activity (please select from the drop-down list)	Description of the activity Max. 200 characters	Leading partner	Date (if relevant)	Place	Target Audiences											Number of people reached	Communication level	Other partners involved	Outcome (e.g. number of participants, number of downloads, etc)	Status	Links to the event or other online resource		
					Industry, business partners	Innovation	EU Institutions	National authorities	Regional authorities	Local authorities	Profession	Citizens	Research communities	Basic and user communities	International organisations (UN, IAEA, OECD, etc)							Investors	Other, please specify in comments
1 Website	KOM was announced on the YTU's website	YTU	20/09/2023	Online	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	60000	National	N/A		https://www.yildiz.edu.tr/universite/haberler/shore-projesinin-kick-etkinligi-gerceklestirildi	
2 Website	Publication of a news article about the launch of the SHORE project (French and English) on Euronovia's	Euronovia	5/10/2023	Online	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	TBC	International	N/A	TBC	Delivered	FR: https://euronovia.eu/lancement-du
3 Social media	Social media posts about the launch of SHORE on Euronovia's accounts	Euronovia	5/10/2023	Online	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		International	N/A	Impressions: 700	Delivered	Tweet: https://twitter.com/euronovia/status/
4 Social media	emphasised the #EUCO2023 mission Charter on social media	GSNE	12/10/2023	Online	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		International	N/A			
5 Social media	repost tacking #ICT's ecological footprint as part of Estonia's national Digital Agenda for 2030	GSNE	30/10/2023	Online													x		National				
6 Newsletter	Announcement of the SHORE Open Call on the Blue Schools Network application deadlines (KUW School Newsletter)	KUW	13/11/2023	Online				x	x	x							x	1600	National			Delivered	to be completed
7 Social media	Participation at the KOM in Istanbul	Mare Nostrum	8/9/2023	Online	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	1300	National	N/A		Delivered	https://www.facebook.com/ongmarenostrom/posts/pfbid031h1Mb2pDNoQ35Bsr75Gu7MCMQDwLvp61RvgtelIhttps://www.facebook.com/tudav/posts/pfbid032AlybQZaFz51W5h3mMUhttps://www.facebook.com/tudav/posts/pfbid03137d4udm7ERWorassuGebaWvfkxGdFruv1e9jhttps://www.facebook.com/tuoav/post/s/pfbid02yastbMkLCAWHFVwnzePadG5kcmhV8GLuFUKDDeLvqzbPMDwGjIwJ2wFce0w1
8 Social media	Announcement of the information about the correlation between SHORE and Blue School Network. Also a brief information about the Blue Schools Network	TUDAV	2/11/2023	Online	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		International	N/A		Delivered	
9 Social media	Announcement of the kick off meeting of SHORE	TUDAV	8/9/2023	Online	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		International	N/A		Delivered	
10 Other: Please specify in the comment	Networking event arranged by the INSI project - promotion of SHORE calls	KUW	21.11.2023	Vienna/Austria														40	Regional		strong interest among participants re. the SHORE Open Calls	Delivered	https://science-education.at/
11 Other: Please specify in the comment	EUCUNET Annual Assembly - promotion of SHORE calls	KUW	6/7.11.2023	Vienna/Austria													x	55	International			Delivered	link to be completed
12 Other: Please specify in the comment	Presentation at BME Children's University	BME	Oct 2024	Budapest													x	500	National		participants	Ongoing	
13 Other: Please specify in the comment	INFO DAYS Webinar to prepare Estonian schools to participate in the Blue Schools Network and SHORE	GSNE	22 Nov 2023	online													x		National		19 schools represented	Delivered	Zoom

Annex 2 – KPIs analysis at M17

Dissemination or communication activity	Tool / Activity	When (and where, if relevant)	KPI	Target at M36	Target at M17	Results at M17	Evaluation - M17				Partner(s) in charge
							High (>100%)	Good (≤ 100%)	Moderate (≤ 75%)	Low (<50%)	
Communication	Project website	M36	No. of visits	20,000	9,444	59,756	>9444	≤9444	≤7083	<4722	EUR
	Social Media	M36	No. of followers	500	236	2,081	>236	≤236	≤177	<118	EUR
	Poster	M6	No. of posters distributed	100	47	30	>47	≤47	≤35	<24	ALL
	Roll-up	M6	No. of roll-up distributed	20	9	9	>9	≤9	≤7	<5	ALL
	Flyer/Brochure	M6	No. of brochure distributed	1000	472	1,293	>472	≤472	≤354	<236	ALL
	Project factsheet/One-page descriptor	M6	No. of factsheet distributed	1000	472	57	>472	≤472	≤354	<236	ALL
	Leaflet/Final brochure	M36	No. of final brochure	2000	N/A	N/A	-	-	-	-	ALL
	Newsletter	Every 6 months, starting at	No. of newsletter	6	2	3	>2	≤2	≤2	<1	EUR
			No. of subscribers	250	118	173	>118	≤118	≤89	<59	
	Press Release	M6 and M36	No. of press releases	2	1	4	>1	≤1	≤1	<1	EUR
	Final Media Press Kit	M36	No. of Press Kit	1	N/A	N/A	-	-	-	-	EUR
	Motion design video	M20	No. of videos	1	N/A	N/A	-	-	-	-	EUR
	Interview of schools and partners	M36	No. of interviews	10	5	5	>5	≤5	≤4	<2	EUR
Public awareness campaign for the open calls	M36	No. of campaigns	3	2	2	>2	≤2	≤2	<1	ALL	
Dissemination	Participation in popularisation events	M36	No. of events	1	0	2	>0	≤0	≤0	<0	ALL
	Mission Ocean Nights	M36	No. of events	2	1	1	>1	≤1	≤1	<1	YTU, UNIPD, WSB, MARE NOSTRUM
	Infoday and conference	M36	No. of events	1	N/A	N/A	-	-	-	-	YTU
	Mission Oceans Helix	M36	No. of community stakeholders	250	118	250	>118	≤118	≤89	<59	CHX
	Clustering and Networking	M36	No. of clustering events	4	2	2	>2	≤2	≤1	<1	CHX
			No. of project collaborations	10	5	4	>5	≤5	≤4	<2	
	Stakeholders' workshops	M36	No. of workshops	3	1	1	>1	≤1	0	-	CHX
			No. of attendees/workshop	50	50	40	>50	≤50	≤38	<25	
Webinars	M36	No. of webinars	2	1	5	>1	≤1	≤1	<0	EUR	
Community activities (workshops, seminars, meetNtalks, etc.)	M36	No. of activities/open call	84	28	55	>28	≤28	≤21	<14	Country Hubs	
Publications	Scientific publications	M36	No. of scientific publications	3	1	5	>1	≤1	≤1	<1	ALL
	Articles in specialised magazines	M36	No. of articles	2	N/A	0	-	-	-	-	ALL

SHORE

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